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ABSTRACT

Technology transfer and human-capital mobility are integral to processes of capacity building that lead to economic and social development. Scientific mobility through institutional channels is argued to be a process in which scientists and engineers can accumulate scientific capitals. This essay reviews the importance of foreign research degrees and postdoctoral positions in the formation of human-capital and social-capital networks. The empirical focus is on six large economies in the Asia-Pacific region, drawing on data from an exploratory survey of scientists publishing in journals indexed in the Science Citation Index (SCI). Mobility for research degrees and postdoctoral research is a significant contributor to the formation of scientific and technical human capital, which has been an important driver in economic expansion and social development in the Asia-Pacific region. The results suggest that destinations for postdoctoral positions are more important than destinations for research degrees in the formation of durable social capital networks. In particular, there appears to a relatively strong relationship between host destinations for postdoctoral-research training and the organization of transnational research collaborations. This finding could have implications for the capacity of developing countries in the Asia-Pacific region to link and integrate into the emerging knowledge hubs within the region.

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER AND MOBILE SCIENTIFIC HUMAN CAPITAL

The relationship between technology transfer and the mobility of human capital is an important contemporary global issue. Skilled migration can be understood as a system of knowledge transactions (Williams, 2007) that add to stocks of tacit knowledge and supplies of embodied skills in particular occupations and locations (Becker, 1964). This creates opportunities for the absorption of knowledge and technology by firms (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990) and in regions (Gertler, 2003). As Mahroum (1999, p. 189) thus describes, “nations increasingly view technology transfer as primarily a people-oriented phenomenon.” With the value of highly skilled “knowledge workers” escalating, as capitalism becomes ever more reliant on the knowledge-generating and value-adding capabilities of science and technology (Kleinman & Vallas, 2001, p. 451; Stehr & Meja, 2001), competition for human resources has become an important dynamic at the firm, regional, and national levels (Turpin, Liu, Garrett-Jones, & Burns, 2002; Zweig, 2006).

The perception of the global sourcing of scientists as competition for scarce human capital stems from at least the 1970s, when economic analyses conceptualized movements of skilled workers from developing to developed nations as a zero-sum game (Bhagwati 1979; Bhagwati & Hamada, 1976). The term “brain drain” had been used for the first time in 1963 in a report by the Royal Society of London in reference to the exodus of British scientists to the United States (Brandi, 2006). In 1975, the U.S. House of Representatives Committee on International Relations examined the question of the brain drain in the context of a study of science, technology, and U.S. diplomacy (U.S. House, 1977, pp. 1037–1318). This report described the brain drain as an issue with three dimensions: 1) a manpower problem that affects growth patterns in both advanced and developing countries; 2) a development problem that “deprives the developing nations of much needed human capital for achieving their major national goal, namely, modernization”; and 3) a science and technology problem related to the “management of resources and the building of infrastructure for modern industrial societies” (U.S. House, 1977, p. 1048). The brain drain, understood in terms of the net gain or loss of human capital, thus came to be recognized as an important factor contributing to emergent patterns of economic and social development (Sen, 1980).

More recently, the zero-sum conception underlying thinking about the brain drain has been challenged. It has been argued that mobility of the highly skilled can have benefits for sending countries (Gaillard & Gaillard, 1997). For developing countries, this has been argued to include creating aspirations for education (Docquier & Rapoport, 2005) and technology transfer through the return of scientists (Ozden & Schiff, 2005). Another challenge to zero-sum conceptions has been research into “distributed” or “diaspora” knowledge networks (DKNs) (Barré, Hernandez, Meyer, & Vinck, 2003; Meyer & Wattiaux, 2006; OECD, 2002, 2008). Such networks, it has been argued, show potential for solving issues confronting both poorer and richer countries (Mahroum & De Guchteneire, 2006; Meyer & Wattiaux, 2006) by “converting the loss of human resources into a remote although accessible asset of expanded networks” (Meyer & Wattiaux, 2006, p. 5). Empirical studies of DKNs have been emerging (Meyer, Brown, & Kaplan, 1999; Stein, Stren, Fitzgibbon, & MacLean, 2001).

Stein and colleagues (2001), for example, have argued that DKNs contribute to innovation and international learning by producing new knowledge through trans-disciplinary research across international boundaries and operational knowledge acquired through

context-bound interactions across various sectors. Their case-study analyses emphasize processes of dissemination through networks that carry global knowledge into local contexts (Stein et al., 2001, p. 4).

Distributed knowledge networks are also a feature of knowledge transfer in the Asia-Pacific region. For example, Biao (2007) has shown how national diaspora networks in the information technology (IT) sectors of India and China have different outcomes in terms of local outputs (socioeconomic development and basic research, respectively) depending on whether they are predominantly framed by commercial actors, including multinational corporations (MNCs) (India) and institutional policies (China). Saxenian (2005) highlights the case of NeWave Semiconductor Co., a Chinese IT startup that drew upon networks in Hong Kong, Taiwan, and the United States. These networks included U.S.-educated Chinese engineers who moved to Taiwan from Silicon Valley during the 1990s, before relocating to the Chinese mainland to take advantage of infrastructure hubs such as Shanghai's Zhangjiang Science Park (Saxenian, 2005, p. 330). Similarly, Ramirez and Dickenson (2007) have shown how the Zhong-guancun Science Park in Beijing has enabled Chinese universities and companies to integrate their research and development (R&D) activities into global scientific and industrial networks with diaspora connections.

Such networks tend to have concentrations in what can be described as "knowledge hubs," which can link to researchers in developing locations. The mobility of researchers can shape the connections and reach of these networks, determining to some extent the resources and capabilities that can be brought to bear on local problems. Thus a key observation is that diasporas of scientific and technological personnel may create positive externalities by providing readily accessible new knowledge, ideas, and skills that depend as much on *where researchers have been* as *where they are currently situated* (Turpin, Woolley, Marceau, & Hill, 2008).

This essay explores one aspect of the complex human-capital mobility that has played a role in integrating the Asia-Pacific region into global science and R&D. The mobility explored is that of scientists and engineers from six large knowledge-producing centers in the region: Australia, China, India, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan. The essay focuses on the participation of scientists and engineers in foreign research degrees and postdoctoral positions, then goes on to analyze correlations between foreign destinations for these professional opportunities and the building of scientific networks and productive research collaborations.

LINKING AND INTEGRATING VIA HUMAN CAPITAL: ASIA-PACIFIC AND GLOBAL SCIENCE

Reflecting more complex understandings of the geographic mobility of human capital and the importance of networking in the contemporary globalized economy, developed and developing nations alike have adopted policies to promote the circulation, return, and recruitment of scientists and technologists (OECD, 1997, 2002, 2008; Zweig, 2006). The European Union has also developed a mobility strategy for the European Research Area that aims both to increase the circulation of researchers within Europe, and to make Europe a more favorable destination for non-European researchers (Ackers, 2004; CEC, 2001).

In the Asia-Pacific region, institutional arrangements and programs have historically focused on sending talented students and researchers to foreign universities, particularly in the United States and Europe. In recent decades, Korea and Taiwan in particular have

benefited from the Ph.D. training of scientists and engineers in the United States, with increasing numbers of these students returning as domestic economic expansion gathered momentum during the 1980s. Once economic expansion became rapid and sustained, Korea experienced a strong flow of returning scientists (Song, 1997), therefore national policy shifted from the use of financial incentives or obligations, which failed to induce Korean scientists and engineers to return, toward policies to best take advantage of the returning human capital attracted by economic and social developments (Song, 1997). During the 1990s, policies such as “Brain Pool” assisted Korean institutions in hiring overseas-based Korean researchers for short visits, explicitly tapping into human capital within the Korean diaspora. There was also a policy emphasis placed on creating postdoctoral positions as labor-market entry points for scientists and engineers who had recently completed their doctorates overseas (Song, 1997, pp. 339–340). At the same time, government support is provided for doctorates earned in Korea to undertake postdoctoral positions overseas (Song, 1997). What is evident in the Korean case is the fundamental relationship among economic and technological development, institutional arrangements, and patterns of mobility of scientists and engineers. As economic development accelerates, mobility is transformed from a brain-drain issue toward a question of how to manage and capitalize on patterns of circulation and diaspora networks, with policy settings having to be adjusted to this evolving context.

In China, the situation can be considered to be evolving, at least to some extent, in a similar pattern to what has happened in Korea and Taiwan. For China, the current drive for scientists and engineers is directly related to the need to capitalize on flows of foreign R&D investment. Both China and India are now attracting significant global investments in R&D from the world’s largest corporations, accompanied by growing flows of scientific personnel (Dente, 2007). A recent study (Goldbrunner, Doz, Wilson, & Veldhoen, 2006) has suggested that the world’s large-business R&D spenders plan to place 77% of new R&D investments in these two rapidly expanding economies over the next decade.

Historically, from the time President Deng Xiaoping advocated the advancement of science and technology during the 1970s, the training of scientific and engineering personnel was a specific priority in China, leading to programs for talented research students to train offshore (Zweig & Rosen, 2003). However, these policies were largely considered a failure due to the failure of approximately two-thirds of participants to return home (Zweig & Rosen, 2003), a situation partly due to restrictions on dual citizenship (Biao, 2003). The situation changed quite dramatically in around 1990, with the implementing of the “twelve words” policy—support for studying overseas; encourage returning from abroad; and freedom to leave or stay—which removed obstacles to overseas travel that had restricted circulation (Biao, 2006; Zweig, 2007). An increased freedom to circulate, combined with a range of policies to support overseas study and attract returning students now operates (Biao, 2006; Zweig, 2007). An important initiative is the provision of appropriate infrastructure to attract science and technology entrepreneurs, with more than 20 science parks for returning students and overseas scholars having been constructed since 2000 (Saxenian, 2005). It is likely that these institutional arrangements and policy settings have reduced what may still remain a net outflow of Chinese scientists and engineers (Saxenian, 2005) at this stage of the social transformation and economic expansion currently underway.

India has also provided a steady flow of scientists and engineers, both students and the already qualified, to developed economies since the 1960s (U.S. House, 1977), despite the relatively large scale of India's public research sector (Krishna & Khadria, 1997). The major beneficiary of these flows has been the United States, with India being relatively slow to develop policies to attempt to ameliorate the negative effects of the brain drain and/or benefit from potential knowledge inflows (Krishna & Khadria, 1997). From the 1980s onward, continuing outflows were largely due to an oversupply of qualified human capital in comparison to the absorptive capacity of domestic sectors (Krishna & Khadria, 1997, p. 377). However, as foreign and domestic investment in industrial sectors, particularly biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, and information and computing technology (ICT), has grown, greater employment and research opportunities have emerged. The ICT sector has derived benefit from the global circulation of Indian human capital, particularly in terms of the return of Indian entrepreneurs to establish startups, thus transferring their knowledge and commercial expertise gained overseas (Biao, 2007).

Australia is a somewhat different case again, having developed an increasingly large and diverse migration program over the past three or four decades as a key driver of economic growth (DIAC, 2006–07). The skilled component of the program has been particularly emphasized in recent years (DIAC, 2006–07). At the same time, the exporting of higher education services to foreign students has opened a pathway for those who gain qualifications in Australian universities to take up residency. Australians desiring to study abroad have long had opportunities available through a range of federal programs. In recent years, programs have also been developed to entice “eminent” Australian overseas-based researchers to return home (ARC, 2008). Australian science- and education-policy documents thus now advocate participation in “brain circulation” in order to ensure that “our brightest researchers are exposed to cutting-edge research environments so that they can bring this knowledge and skill back to Australia” (DEST, 2006, p. 67), while at the same time promoting the creation of skilled migration and education pathways for migrants “leaving their country of origin to seek opportunities in Australia” (DEST, 2006, p. 68).

While linking into education and research systems in North America and Europe has been historically important for capacity-building in the Asia-Pacific region, the most important transformative dynamic in the global mobility of scientists has been the contemporary emergence of Northeast and Southeast Asia as significant locii for foreign direct investment; the production of scientific knowledge and technology; and for expenditure on R&D (Goldbrunner et al., 2006). China and Korea in particular have rapidly increased their shares of knowledge production as measured by indicators such as the Science Citation Index (SCI) (Leydesdorff & Zhou, 2005; Zhou & Leydesdorff, 2006). The numbers of scientists and engineers being educated in Asia has also been growing strongly (NSB, 2006), a factor directly linked to economic expansion and social transformation in the region. The greater integration of Northeast and Southeast Asia into “global science” and shares of global R&D expenditure is itself undoubtedly linked to the historical migration of skilled personnel: between 1962 and 1966, more than 45% of engineers and natural scientists accepted by the United States as immigrants were from India and China (U.S. House, 1977). The involvement of migrant researchers and entrepreneurs in the development of innovation hubs such as Silicon Valley is well-known. Scientists and engineers who have honed their research skills and developed commercial know-how in such R&D-intensive settings have subsequently been important in the emergence of

Northeast and Southeast Asian centers as knowledge producers, whether they remain overseas or return home. The mobility of highly skilled human capital has thus been an important factor in the integration of the Asia-Pacific region into the global economy.

Contemporary geographic mobility of scientists can thus be understood both as a driver and a consequence of competition for human capital and the increasingly globalized organization of scientific work (Mahroum, 2000). Very different levels of scientific capability remain distributed across the Asia-Pacific region, and the circulation of human capital remains an important aspect of capacity-building and economic expansion throughout the region. A future challenge is how smaller developing countries in the region can link into its emerging regional knowledge hubs (InterAcademy Council, 2004; Turpin & Krishna, 2007). This essay suggests that scientific mobility can play an important role in processes of linking and integrating via transnational collaboration and technology transfer. However, before presenting the data and results, the following section defines what is meant by “scientific mobility” and describes its role in the accumulation of forms of scientific capital.

SCIENTIFIC MOBILITY AND THE ACCUMULATION OF SCIENTIFIC CAPITAL

“Scientific mobility” is defined by Mahroum (2000, p. 367) as “crossborder physical and geographic movement that comprises a stay in another country of no less than one year.” The qualifying period of one year separates scientific mobility from visits, conferences, and other forms of professional circulation, implying a period of work and engagement in a foreign laboratory. Mahroum argues that such scientific mobility “goes through channels of institutions that enjoy a high reputation for excellence and expertise” (2000, p. 367). The universities, research institutes, and laboratories that are the principal sites of research degrees and postdoctoral positions (Melin, 2004), along with the government-funding programs underpinning these arrangements, provide the organizational and institutional contexts for these movements. The movement of scientists to foreign institutions for postgraduate research degrees and/or early-career postdoctoral positions sits within this definition of “scientific mobility through channels of institutions.”

Scientific mobility can be understood from the perspective of the accumulation of forms of scientific capital. Following Bozeman, Dietz, and Gaughan (2001), we conceive of scientists within the theoretical framework of “scientific and technical human capital” (STHC). The concept of STHC pairs an “expanded notion of human capital [with a] productive social capital network” (Bozeman et al., 2001, p. 718) to construct a model in which the individual acquiring and enhancing of capabilities (human capital) and the collective building of networks and collaborative teams in science (social capital) are understood as a process “so fundamental, intimate, and dynamic that neither concept is fully meaningful by itself” (Bozeman et al., 2001, p. 723). Capital accumulation in science is thus the process through which individuals engage in human-capital formation while simultaneously building the personal and professional relationships that build their social-capital network. Scientific mobility can be understood as a process through which individuals seek to simultaneously enhance their individual capabilities (human capital), but also to become integrated into, and build, research collectives and professional connections (social capital). Mobility is thus a factor contributing to scientists’ “sustained ability to contribute and enhance their capabilities” (Bozeman et al., 2001, p. 718).

The importance of scientific mobility for processes of knowledge transfer can thus be conceived as having three interrelated dimensions: first, the formation of human capital is enhanced through the acquisition in foreign institutions of knowledge and skills that may not be available in the sending country; second, scientific social-capital networks are built via collocation with peers in foreign universities and research laboratories; and last, there is potential for these social-capital networks to operate as “conduits of knowledge” (OECD, 2008; Turpin et al., 2008) that can leverage information, expertise, and knowledge “at a distance” or, even more compellingly, to operate as a form of organization of knowledge production that generates collaborative research outputs.

This essay thus seeks to answer questions about the role of scientific mobility for research degrees and postdoctoral positions in the formation of human capital, the building of social-capital networks, and in the leveraging of these networks via collaborative projects. There is a significant literature that underlines the importance of postdoctoral positions in building scientific capital, which provides an expectation that postdoctoral positions will be a relatively more important variable than research degrees in our data. Melin (2004) and Zubieta (2009) have found that postdoctoral mobility is a source of integration into social-capital networks.

Melin (2004) found that in the course of postdoctoral research in foreign countries, Swedish researchers built social-capital networks that “persisted” over time. These networks were heavily focused in North America and Europe and at least to some extent reproduced networks of more senior colleagues. Unlike the situation in some U.S. university departments, where postdoctoral positions can be a low-paid career dead-end (Nerad & Cerny, 1999), these positions are often highly sought after and selective labor-market entry points in Europe, Japan (Lancio-Morandat & Nohara, 2002), and Australia (Marceau & Preston, 1997). Postdoctoral positions in prestigious research institutes, laboratories, and universities can provide access to cutting-edge technologies, relatively abundant resources, and elite research networks. The taking up of a postdoctoral research position is thus a key strategy for many recently trained scientists (Melin, 2004; Lancio-Morandat & Nohara, 2002; Marceau & Preston, 1997).

THE STUDY AND DATA

The data described here come from an exploratory survey of mainly natural and physical scientists and engineers. The participants were drawn from a sample of published journal-article authors, whose e-mail addresses were sourced from the SCI database (the social sciences and humanities are included in a separate database not used in this study). All available authors’ e-mail addresses for SCI indexed papers in 2004 were exported from the database, provided that the published article included at least one author from 22 Asia-Pacific locations (see Table 1). This information was collated according to the country of the lead author. From this raw list, addresses were compiled for each of the 22 locations in approximate proportion to the number of journal articles from these locations published in SCI journals in 2004. The number of e-mails actually delivered was estimated at 50,000, with another large number not deliverable (n approximately = 20,000). The number of successfully delivered e-mails that were read and discarded by potential respondents is unknown, making meaningful calculation of a response rate impossible. The e-mail message invited participation in an online survey. It contained a link to a project- and survey-information page, along with an individual identification number and password to access the survey. The information page was available in Chinese, English, Japanese, and

Korean; the survey, however, was only available in English. The total number of useable responses received was 10,132 (this total includes co-authors from outside the Asia-Pacific region), of which 8,008 were from the 22 locations targeted in the initial search of the SCI. Table 1 shows the nominated nationality and gender of respondents from Asia-Pacific locations.

Table 1
ASIA-PACIFIC RESPONDENTS' NOMINATED NATIONALITY
AND GENDER

Nationality*	Male	Female	Total	%
Australia	795	239	1,034	12.9
Bangladesh	68	3	71	0.9
China	1,449	193	1,642	20.5
Hong Kong	44	6	50	0.6
India	1,435	226	1,661	20.7
Indonesia	30	9	39	0.5
Japan	1,241	69	1,310	16.4
Korea	689	47	736	9.2
Malaysia	110	46	156	1.9
New Zealand	240	74	314	3.9
Pakistan	82	16	98	1.2
Papua New Guinea	4	0	4	0.0
Philippines	29	26	55	0.7
Singapore	96	19	115	1.4
Sri Lanka	33	10	43	0.5
Taiwan	371	58	429	5.4
Thailand	121	96	217	2.7
Tonga	0	1	1	0.0
Vietnam	27	6	33	0.4
TOTALS	6,864	1,144	8,008	99.8**

*No responses were received from nationals of Fiji, Vanuatu, or Western Samoa;

**≠ 100 due to rounding.

Respondents were predominantly male (87%). Many nationalities had proportions of female respondents higher than the overall level of 13%, including: Australia (23%); India (13.6%); Indonesia (23.1%); Malaysia (29.5%); New Zealand (23.6%); Pakistan (16.3%); Philippines (47.3%); Sri Lanka (23.3%); Taiwan (13.5%); Thailand (44.2%); and Vietnam (18.2%). The low overall rate was due to the small proportion of female respondents from two national groups that together made up one-quarter of the Asia-Pacific total: Japan (5.3% female respondents); and Korea (6.4%). The varying participation of female respondents is no doubt due to diverse cultural and institutional factors influencing women's participation in science and engineering careers in particular countries—factors that will have also changed over time. As a broad point of comparison, the proportion of

science and engineering doctorates awarded to women in the United States has risen from 9% in 1973 to 33% in 2006 (NSB, 2008).

In terms of scientific areas, respondents were asked about the field of their doctoral degree. Table 2 indicates the number of doctoral degrees among respondents from each national group, by broad scientific areas. The basic sciences (life sciences, chemistry, physics), engineering, and medical science (basic medical and clinical medicine) are the largest groups among respondents. Differences among national systems are clearly evident. Among the six largest national groups that are the focus of the results of this essay, there were clear biases toward particular fields among respondents. Australian respondents were clustered in medical and life sciences, with only small proportions of chemists and engineers. Chinese respondents were mainly engineers, chemists, or physicists. Indian respondents were more evenly distributed across scientific fields, including large numbers of physicists. Japanese respondents were also well distributed across fields, but with the largest number in medical sciences, while Korean respondents were heavily concentrated in engineering. Respondents from Taiwan were clustered in the medical and engineering fields.

Table 2
RESPONDENTS WITH RESEARCH DEGREE, BY BROAD FIELD OF DEGREE (%)*

Nationality	N.	Agric.	Med.	Life	Chem.	Eng.	Earth & comp.	Math	Phys.	Other
Australia	903	5.2	21.5	21.9	6.8	6.5	8.5	10.9	10.5	8.2
Bangladesh	58	10.3	6.9	10.3	12.1	24.1	5.2	8.6	10.3	12.1
China	1,416	2.6	6.9	6.6	15.5	24.6	9.8	16.9	12.9	4.2
Hong Kong	42	0.0	21.4	11.9	9.5	16.7	7.1	19.0	11.9	2.4
India	1,431	3.6	11.9	16.1	16.1	14.0	5.7	6.5	18.2	7.8
Indonesia	37	5.4	5.4	13.5	10.8	32.4	2.7	10.8	13.5	5.4
Japan	1,152	7.3	23.9	12.4	14.0	13.4	6.6	4.9	12.8	4.9
Korea	639	2.7	14.2	10.0	9.4	31.5	5.0	12.1	11.6	3.6
Malaysia	132	3.0	19.7	12.9	10.6	28.8	2.3	7.6	6.8	8.3
New Zealand	273	5.5	17.2	24.5	11.4	6.2	7.3	9.2	8.1	10.6
Pakistan	71	11.3	18.3	21.1	12.7	9.9	4.2	7.0	7.0	8.5
Papua New Guinea	4	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	0.0	25.0
Philippines	47	14.9	14.9	25.5	4.3	2.1	0.0	4.3	14.9	19.1
Singapore	95	1.1	14.7	9.5	6.3	34.7	0.0	13.7	6.3	13.7
Sri Lanka	37	10.8	16.2	24.3	8.1	10.8	8.1	8.1	8.1	5.4
Taiwan	335	4.8	20.3	9.0	9.3	25.7	6.9	9.3	7.5	7.5
Thailand	184	6.5	29.9	14.1	10.9	14.7	1.6	2.2	3.3	16.8
Vietnam	30	3.3	3.3	10.0	10.0	20.0	3.3	26.7	16.7	6.7
TOTALS	6,886	4.5	15.7	13.5	12.6	17.7	6.8	9.9	12.5	6.7

*Includes completed doctoral and masters degrees by research.

There are clear limitations to the data gathered through this exploratory survey. As with the data for gender participation (Table 1), the distribution of respondents by field is not necessarily representative of the overall science system in the different countries. In the first place, the sampling undertaken through the SCI database biases the survey respondents toward researchers producing English-language journal articles. Moreover, the sampling process did not attempt to include any historical perspective, but collected authors' addresses only for one year (2004). The results described in the following sections should therefore not be considered as representative. Another limitation of the results shown here relates to the age of respondents. Due to insufficient space, the analysis is not broken down into different age groupings; the results given thus aggregate scientific mobility that has occurred across a very broad historical period and do not show transformations in patterns of movement over time. Nevertheless, due to the large numbers of respondents from Australia, China, India, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan, the

results that follow can likely be considered as relatively reliable indicators of broad mobility patterns and network- building activity for these national groups.

FOREIGN RESEARCH DEGREES

To what extent do scientists from the Asia-Pacific region go to foreign institutions for their research training? And where do they go? Table 3 shows the number and rate of foreign research degrees for the six largest respondent groups, along with the most frequent host destinations. A total of 1,225 (18.3%) of all respondents from these six locations obtained their research degrees overseas, equivalent to 20.3% of all those who had research degrees. There are three distinct results evident in these data. First, there is a marked diversity in the rates of foreign research degrees awarded to respondents from the different locations shown. The rate of foreign research degrees among Japanese respondents is very low. This is consistent with the organization of the Japanese science and research systems, in which researchers tend to establish a faculty position before taking up opportunities for international experience (Whitley, 2000). Rates of foreign research degrees are relatively high for the “new economies” of Korea and Taiwan, which is consistent with the human-capital capacity-building necessary for rapid processes of industrialization and economic expansion that have occurred relatively recently in these countries.

Table 3
FOREIGN RESEARCH DEGREES, RATES, AND DESTINATIONS

	FOREIGN RESEARCH DEGREES				
	Respondents (no.)*	No.	Rate (%)	Destinations (no.)	Destinations (%)
Australia	920	213	24.2	27	UK 43.7, US 17.8, NZ 8
China	1,447	302	20.9	32	Japan 17.9, US 16.9, Singapore 13.2, Hong Kong 8.9, UK 7.3, Germany 6, France 4
India	1,478	209	14.1	28	US 47.4, UK 14.8, Canada 4.8, Japan 2.9, Singapore 2.9
Japan	1,171	47	4.0	10	US 55.3, UK 17
Korea	663	258	38.9	13	US 70.9, Japan 12.8, Germany 3.1, UK 3.1
Taiwan	349	196	56.2	15	US 76, UK 7.7, Japan 4.1
TOTALS	6,037	1,225	20.3	n/a	n/a

*Number of respondents with research degrees.

Respondents from Australia (27 destinations), China (32), and India (28) undertook research degrees in a much greater variety of international destinations than did respondents from Japan (10), Korea (13), and Taiwan (15). This is likely to be explained, at least in part, by factors related to broader patterns of global migration. In the Chinese and Indian cases, their international diasporas are very large, and nationals from these countries undertaking research degrees may already be residing in international locations. In the case of Australia, there are large volumes of inward migration flows, particularly in recent years of skilled workers (DEST, 2006).¹ Some Australian respondents brought research qualifications with them in migrating (Woolley & Turpin, 2009); however, this entanglement of scientists in more general human-migration patterns in the Australian case does not alter the potential significance of research degrees for the formation of international networks and collaborations.

Second, the foreign research training undertaken by respondents was concentrated in a small number of host destinations. The United States was the most common destination for international research degrees for all respondent groups except Australia and China. In the former case, this can be explained by colonial ties to the United Kingdom, which was the largest supplier of research degrees to Australian respondents as well as the migration flow described above. Respondents from China were the only group that was more inclined to stay within the Asia-Pacific region moving abroad for research degrees, with Japan and Singapore the major destinations involved. This interpretation is further supported by the fact that Australian survey respondents had completed their undergraduate degree in no fewer than 41 different international locations, compared to China (20), Korea (14), India (13), Japan (9), and Taiwan (6).

Third, most of the foreign degrees awarded were from outside the Asia-Pacific region, with the exception of the Chinese respondents. Overall, Chinese respondents were quite evenly divided among the Asia-Pacific region, the United States, and Europe in terms of where they trained. An explanation for the apparent difference between these respondents and the other groups shown in these data is likely to be found in specific political and social factors. The respondent cohort from China was noticeably younger as a group than all others, which is likely to reflect the opening up of China during the 1970s and the relatively recent integration of the country into “global science.” Greater opportunities for undertaking research degrees in Asia have also been available in recent years, with the emergence of Singapore and Hong Kong alongside Japan as training destinations.

In summary, these data show that research training provides links into the most developed science systems at an early career stage. Although data is not available on the relative quality of institutions and organizations in which respondents trained, a general statement can be made that such training would be intended to gain access to “leading-edge” knowledge, techniques, and technologies. The host destinations involved show that research degree opportunities have indeed been taken up in the “centers” of North American and European science.

FOREIGN POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCH POSITIONS

To what extent do scientists from the Asia-Pacific region go to foreign institutions to take up postdoctoral research positions? And where do they go? More is known about the postdoc patterns of movement of researchers. Melin (2004) studied the movements of 284 Swedish postdocs abroad, finding that almost half went to the United States (48.6%), with other significant proportions going to the United Kingdom (8.8%), Australia (6.7%), France (4.9%), and Germany (3.2%) (p. 97). Melin found that Swedish postdocs were tightly clustered in 25 countries, mainly in Europe and North America, although within these host countries, there were 176 different host universities (p. 98).

Table 4 summarizes the number and rate of foreign postdoctoral research positions and the most frequent host destinations—again, for the six largest respondent groups, by nationality. The total of 3,244 respondents who had previously, or were currently, holders of postdoctoral positions was over half (53.7%) of the group of survey respondents with research degrees from the six Asia-Pacific locations ($n = 6,037$ [Table 3]).

The 1,954 respondents who had taken up a postdoctoral research position in a foreign country amounted to 32.4% of this group, which leads to an important observation: that

this is a considerably higher rate of mobility to foreign institutions than was found among the same group of respondents at the level of research degrees (20.3% [Table 3]). Among respondents who held postdocs, three-fifths (60.2%) did so at a foreign institution (Table 4).

Table 4
FOREIGN POSTDOCTORAL POSITIONS, RATES, AND DESTINATIONS

	FOREIGN POSTDOCTORAL POSITIONS				
	Respondents (no.)*	No.	Rate (%)	Destinations (no.)	Destinations (%)
Australia	511	271	53	27	US 40.6, UK 21.4, Canada 12.2, Germany 4.4, France 3, Japan 2.6
China	724	397	54.8	39	US 25.2, Japan 16.9, Germany 8.1 France 7.1, Singapore 7.1, Hong Kong 5.3, UK 4.8
India	820	519	63.3	38	US 43.5, Germany 11.8, Canada 6.2, Japan 5.8, France 3.5, Australia 2.3, Sweden 2.3
Japan	621	400	64.4	26	US 68.3, Canada 7.3, Germany 5.8, UK 5
Korea	417	292	70	16	US 73.6, Japan 7.9, Canada 4.5, Germany 4.5
Taiwan	151	75	49.7	8	US 80, UK 5.7, Canada 4, Germany 4
TOTALS	3,244	1,954	60.2	n/a	80.4

*Number of respondents holding postdoctoral positions (current and previous).

The higher rate of mobility at the level of postdocs is largely due to the participation of Japanese researchers. Whereas there was negligible mobility for research degrees among Japanese respondents, they were mobile at a rate slightly above that for the six-country group as whole at the postdoctoral level. This mobility was heavily concentrated in the United States. The international mobility patterns of Japanese researchers, both in terms of career timing and overseas destinations, appear relatively clearly defined and having a quite-distinctive national basis.

The United States was the major location for postdocs for respondents from all national groups, with particularly large proportions of those from Taiwan, Korea, and Japan heading to the country during this stage of their research careers. Germany was the most prominent among European destinations, particularly for Indian and Chinese respondents; Japan was the most important Asian destination, with Singapore also emerging. The most diverse group in terms of destinations were those from China, who also reported the lowest level of participation in the U.S. system at the postdoc level. Canada and the United Kingdom were also prominent destinations though overall, diversity in the mix of destinations for postdocs was less marked than at the doctorate level.

In summary, the data presented here suggest that significant proportions of scientific human capital from the major knowledge-producing locations in the Asia-Pacific region are formed through research training and early career research positions in foreign destinations. This scientific mobility is concentrated strongly in North America, particularly in the United States. In Europe, Germany is the most prominent location for links with the Asia-Pacific region, particularly with the Indian research community and the largest knowledge-producing center in the region, Japan. Within the Asia-Pacific region, Japan is the most prominent destination for researchers from elsewhere in the region to

train. The emergence of Singapore as a destination for training and as a node in transnational research networks is noteworthy and reflects the concerted strategy and expenditure on developing a strong higher-education export sector as part of an open, developed economy (Turpin & Krishna, 2007).

SCIENTIFIC MOBILITY, NETWORK BUILDING, AND RESEARCH COLLABORATION

The descriptive analysis in the previous section shows strong levels of scientific mobility for research degrees and postdoctoral positions among respondents. This was particularly the case among those who had held a postdoctoral position, with 60% of these undertaken in foreign countries. Having established the prevalence of these forms of scientific mobility among our respondents, we can move to the questions of the formation of social-capital networks and productive transnational research collaborations.

To what extent are choices about host destinations indicative of the subsequent distribution of scientific networks and research collaborators? The distinction between networks and collaboration in the data is a significant conceptual one. International research networks can be conceived of as vital conduits for the sharing of techniques and the circulation of knowledge. Collaborative research projects are a particular form of the transnational organization of knowledge production. Obviously, research networks and transnational research collaborations may partly or largely overlap. While research projects can be conceived of as goal-directed activity, occurring often in the context of specific epistemic communities, they may be significantly mapped onto more diffuse networks of communication and knowledge-sharing. To a significant extent, research collaborations may formalize institutionally (and support financially) the ongoing activities of research networks. The important point is that while *technology transfers* can occur through both these avenues—building and expanding human and social capital in the process—*research collaboration* refers to the leveraging of distributed networks in goal-directed projects that seek to produce specific research results or outputs.

The indicator of research collaboration we used was the production of some form of codified knowledge. While such productive activity was likely to take place within the context of social-capital networks, it was considered to be qualitatively different to maintaining network contacts and running professional organizations and knowledge-sharing activities, for example. To distinguish between social-capital networking activity and productive research collaboration, our survey asked two different questions:

1) Participants were requested to identify the most significant international locations of their research networks. 2) Participants were asked separately about their most important transnational research collaboration (if they had one): With researchers from which country was the collaborative project undertaken? What was the topic? What research outputs (e.g., papers, patents, and so on) did the collaboration produce? As an indication, a total of 95.3% of the respondents who had done postdoctoral work in a foreign country described a transnational knowledge-producing collaboration. The most common outputs from these collaborations included: co-authored journal articles (72.8%); conference presentations (43.8%); research proposals or grant applications (35.2%); new or improved industrial products or processes (11.1%); and patents (7.4%).

To test the significance of relationships between scientific mobility and research network formation and research collaboration, statistical analyses were undertaken using Pearson's correlation coefficient and Fisher's test of two independent correlation

coefficients (Howell, 1997, p. 261). The results of the Pearson's correlation coefficient tests are shown in Table 5.

Correlations between the variable of foreign research-degree destination and the location of respondents' international research networks were significant for Chinese, Indian, Korean, and Taiwanese respondents ($p < 0.01$), but no significant relationship was found in the cases of Australian and Japanese ones. Correlations between the variable of foreign research-degree destination and the location of respondents' collaborative research partners were significant for Chinese, Indian, Korean, and Taiwanese respondents ($p < 0.01$) and for Japanese respondents ($p < 0.05$), though no significant relationship was found in the case of those from Australia.

Correlations between the variable of foreign postdoctoral-position destination and the location of both the respondents' international research networks and collaborative research partners were significant for all groups ($p < 0.01$). In relation to the location of international research networks, correlations with the destinations of postdoctoral positions were stronger than those for destinations for research degrees in the cases of Australia, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan. In the cases of China and India, however, these correlations were near identical. In relation to the location of international collaborative partners, correlations with postdoc destinations were stronger than those for research degree destinations in all cases except Japan.

Table 5 indicates that foreign postdoctoral destinations have more of an impact on both dimensions (networks and collaborations) than do foreign research-degree destinations. This proposition was tested using Fisher's test of two independent correlation coefficients, which confirmed a difference between the variables of postdoc destinations and research degree destinations on the dimension of locations of research project collaborators, except in the case of Japan, whereas there was no difference with respect to the locations of research networks, except in the case of Australia (Table 6).

Table 5
PEARSON'S CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS AND DESTINATIONS
FOR RESEARCH TRAINING AND POSTDOCTORAL POSITIONS,
WITH LOCATIONS OF RESEARCH NETWORKS AND COLLABORATIVE
PROJECTS

	RESEARCH TRAINING DESTINATION			POSTDOC POSITION DESTINATION		
	No.	Network	Collab- oration	No.	Network	Collab- oration
Australia	213	.075	.030	271	.236 ²	.294 ²
China	302	.379 ²	.268 ²	397	.370 ²	.479 ²
India	209	.428 ²	.322 ²	519	.411 ²	.476 ²
Japan	47	.143	.294 ¹	400	.291 ²	.281 ²
Korea	258	.465 ²	.359 ²	292	.510 ²	.504 ²
Taiwan	196	.511 ²	.211 ²	75	.603 ²	.488 ²
TOTALS	1,225			1,954		

¹ $p < 0.05$; ² $p < 0.01$.

The results shown in Table 6 suggest that foreign postdoctoral destinations are a more significant determinant of the organization of transnational collaborative-research projects than foreign research-degree destinations. The exception to this is the case of the Japanese respondents, for whom no difference could be expected due to their lack of participation in mobility for foreign research degrees. The results also indicate that

research training and postdoctoral destinations have an approximately similar impact on the locations of international networks. The exception to this is the case of Australian respondents, for whom foreign postdoctoral destinations were a more significant predictor of research network locations than foreign research-degree destinations.

Table 6
FISHER'S TEST OF TWO INDEPENDENT
CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS: RESEARCH
TRAINING DESTINATION VS. POSTDOCTORAL
POSITION DESTINATION

	<i>Network</i>	<i>Collaboration</i>
Australia	1.78 ¹	3.24 ²
China	-0.08	3.20 ²
India	-0.22	2.25 ¹
Japan	0.99	-0.07
Korea	0.69	2.07 ¹
Taiwan	0.94	2.30 ¹

¹p < 0.05; ²p < 0.01.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

At the outset, we asked to what extent our survey respondents had been involved in the indivisible processes of forming human-capital and building social-capital networks through experience in foreign countries, experience gained through scientific mobility via institutional channels for research degrees and postdoctoral positions. Among respondents from our six focus countries, one-fifth of those with research degrees had gained them in foreign institutions. At the level of postdocs, foreign institutions hosted almost one-third of these respondents, equivalent to three-fifths of those who had undertaken postdoc positions. Global scientific mobility thus makes a significant contribution to enhancing the capabilities of scientific and technical human capital (STHC) from the Asia- Pacific region.

Overall, the pattern of the scientific mobility of respondents from the Asia-Pacific region was shown to be broadly consistent with that described by Melin (2004) among Swedish postdocs, in that the largest proportions of mobile researchers circulated through the “scientific centers” or “knowledge hubs” of North America and Europe. The United States was shown to be the knowledge hub that has attracted most respondents from the Asia-Pacific region for research degrees and postdoctoral research positions.

However, diversity was also evident in comparing the mobility patterns of different national groups. Researchers from the more recently and rapidly industrializing economies of Korea and Taiwan were particularly strongly concentrated in the United States as a host destination. Respondents from China were more diffused in their destination choices, including being more strongly inclined toward foreign destinations within Asia than other groups, particularly toward Japan and Singapore. The development of circulation between India and Germany was also an interesting feature. The high number of different mobility destinations among respondents from China and India suggests more of a willingness to explore spaces outside North America and Europe than was found by Melin (2004). However, also noticeable in these data was the almost entire absence of scientific mobility between China and India.

National science and education systems are also a factor. Respondents from Japan confirmed the distinct structure of Japanese scientific mobility, with very low levels of foreign research degrees contrasting with levels on a parity with other national groups for foreign postdoctoral positions—the vast majority of which being situated in the United States. The high levels of scientific mobility among respondents from China, Korea, and Taiwan reflect strong policy emphasis over several decades on creating programs to assist the circulation of talented researchers in the interests of knowledge and technology transfer to build capacity at home. As was described in the introduction to this essay, studies increasingly show benefits for home countries despite whether these individuals return or remain foreign-based. It is also increasingly evident that the different national institutional and organizational contexts of mobility and network activity tend to produce different types of benefits.

We also asked to what extent destinations for scientific mobility correlate to the distribution of research networks and the organization of transnational knowledge-producing collaborations among respondents. The correlations were positive and significant for research degrees and networks, with the exception of Australian and Japanese respondents, and for research degrees and collaborations, with the exception of Australian respondents. For all respondent groups, the correlations were positive and significant for postdocs and networks and for postdocs and collaborations. The strength of the correlations was not such that the importance of destinations for research degrees or postdocs should be overestimated as a factor in the distribution of networks and collaborations. Nevertheless, correlations for postdocs and both networks and collaborations were relatively strong for respondents from China, India, Korea, and Taiwan and strongly suggest that such mobility is a factor that matters in determining social capital networks.

Broader currents of human migration also appeared to be a factor entangled in the scientific mobility observed, particularly in relation to Australian respondents. The relatively high level of participation of Australian respondents in foreign research degrees did not translate into a significant factor in social-capital network-building or transnational collaborative projects. The explanation for this is very likely due to the relatively high levels of Australian nationals who moved to Australia as skilled migrants *subsequent* to obtaining their research degrees.

More generally, as we had expected from other literature, these results suggest that postdoctoral positions are more significant than research degrees in the formation of social-capital networks. The analysis clearly found postdoc positions to be more important in relation to the leveraging of social-capital networks in the production of scientific knowledge. As Melin (2004, p. 101) found, social-capital networks formed through postdoctoral positions tend to persist over time; however, what Melin (2004) was unable to determine was whether such persistence over time had any relationship to knowledge-producing collaborations, or whether it remained at the level of information exchange, professional activities, and the like. Our analyses found the strongest relationship to be between foreign postdoctoral positions and knowledge-producing collaborations. The vast majority (95%) of respondents who held foreign postdocs were involved in transnational collaborations that had knowledge outputs. Probably the most important contribution this present essay makes, therefore, is to show that social-capital networks built via scientific mobility for postdoctoral research positions make a positive

subsequent contribution to transnational knowledge-production activity. Additionally, as evidence of a sustained effort of collaboration, such activity is also an indicator of the durability over time of social-capital networks formed at the postdoctoral level.

In conclusion, scientific mobility through institutional channels is a significant factor in processes of human-capital formation and social-capital network-building that link regions into knowledge hubs. As this essay has described, networks built at the postdoctoral level appear to have a positive impact on productive forms of collaboration at a distance. These processes highlight the importance not just of where researchers are located, but also where they have been, in thinking about human resources for science, technology, and development. A key empirical question remains to be investigated, however, regarding the extent to which the resources of these networks built through scientific mobility are being brought to bear on “local problems” that may be spatially removed from knowledge hubs, relative to the extent to which they are organized around the important scientific problems defined by global science.

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